

STUDIES ON GROUND WATER IN ARARIA DISTRICT (BIHAR) FOCUSING ON ITS PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Ashok Kumar* , **R. B. Jha,**** **Arun Kumar**
University Department of Zoology
B.N.Mandal University, Madhepura
*Research Scholar ** Supervisor

Abstract

The water samples of different sources i.e. tube well, pond, well and river covering the whole district of Araria was analysed for the physico chemical parameters for pH, Alkalinity, Fluoride, Chloride, Dissolved solids, Carbon dioxide, BOD, COD, Iron and Arsenic. The results revealed that the findings are within the permissible limit for the drinking water as per the BIS recommendations.

Key Words: BIS recommendations, BOD, COD, Iron and Arsenic, physic-chemical parameters

Introduction

Water is extremely essential for survival of all living organisms. The quality of water is vital concern for mankind since it is directly linked with human welfare. In India, most of the population is dependent on groundwater as the only source of drinking water supply. The groundwater is believed to be comparatively much clean and free from pollution than surface water. But prolonged discharge of industrial effluents, domestic sewage and solid waste dump causes the groundwater to become polluted and created health problems. The problems of groundwater quality are much more acute in the areas which are densely populated, thickly industrialized and have shallow groundwater tables. The rapid growth of urban areas has further affected groundwater quality due to overexploitation of resources and improper waste disposal practices. Hence, there is always a need for and concern over the protection and management of groundwater quality. Considering the above aspects of groundwater contamination, the present study was undertaken to investigate the possible impact of the groundwater quality of some open wells and one municipal water sample in Amalner town of Jalgaon district of North Maharashtra

region. Thus, in this paper an attempt has been made to assess the physical and chemical properties of groundwater (open well, tube well) and comparing.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

The sampling point of different resources of drinking water were chosen in such a way that the entire area of the District Araria may be covered, so that the quality of draining water of the entire District may be assessed and the results obtained may serve the purpose more correctly.

For the present study of quality assessment of drinking water of Araria district, 25 open well, 20 hands pumps, 10 tube wells, one pond and four river ghats have been selected for sampling covering the entire area of the District. The samples were analysed for pH, Alkalinity, Fluoride, Chloride, Dissolved solids, Carbon dioxide, BOD, COD, iron and Arsenic by Standard methods (APHA...)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Table – 1: Average value of different parameters

Parameters (ppm)	Well Water Samples	Hand Pump Samples	Tube Well Samples	Pond Samples	River Samples
1. pH	8.10 ±0.47	7.90± 0.06	7.49± 0.15	8.35± 0.06	8.22± 0.21
2. Alkalinity	375.91±78.44	343.80 ± 7.75	291.40± 14.94	379.5± 2.121	332.75 ± 30.78
3. Fluoride	1.0708 ± 0.44	0.943 ± 0.038	0.729± 0.349	0.875± 0.063	0.577± 0.080
4. Chloride	17.609± 7.019	9.8155± 0.489	8.143± 1.137	10.41± 0.028	9.982± 0.956
5. Dissolved Solids	247.32± 58.80	172.00± 22.72	122.40± 15.95	315.50± 7.778	428.25± 13.64
6. Dissolved Carbon dioxide	32.56 ± 4.59	23.058 ± 0.327	19.92±0.42	47.50 ± 2.121	46.50 ± 2.645
7. BOD	1.132 ± 0.258	0.596± 0.047	0.439±0.04	4.215± 0.148	3.315 ± 0.011
8. COD	3.224 ± 0.333	1.439 ± 0.122	0.809±0.05	4.295± 0.0070	5.375± 0.034
9. Iron	0.327 ± 0.417	0.074± 0.01	0.035±0.013	1.055± 0.205	1.09± 0.118
10. Arsenic	0.04 ± 0.005	0.031 ± 0.005	0.017±0.006	0.015± 0.007	0.01± 0.00

Table–2: The permissible value, desirable values of BIS and maximum allowable limit of WHO

Parameters	Desirable limit	Permissible limit	WHO allowable limit
1. pH	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5
2. Alkalinity	200mg/L	600mg/L	---
3. Fluoride	1.0mg/L	1.5mg/L	1.5mg/L
4. Chloride	250mg/L	1000mg/L	250mg/L
5. Dissolved Solids	500mg/L	2000mg/L	1000mg/L
6. Dissolved CO ₂	-	-	-
7. BOD	1-2ppm	3-5ppm	3-5ppm
8. COD	-	-	-
9. Iron	0.3mg/L	1.0mg/L	0.3mg/L
10. Arsenic	0.05mg/L	No relaxation	0.05mg/L

pH

pH is a term used universally to express the intensity of the acid or alkaline condition of a solution. Most of the waters are slightly alkaline due to presence of carbonates and bicarbonates. The pH values of water samples varied between 7.1 to 8.0 and were found within the limit prescribed by WHO.

Dissolved oxygen (DO)

Dissolved oxygen is important parameter in water quality assessment and reflects the physical and biological processes prevailing in the water. The DO values indicate the degree of pollution in water bodies. DO values varied from 2.2 to 8.3. The sampling points S2 and S3 showed low DO values indicating heavy contamination by organic matter.

Alkalinity

Alkalinity of water is its capacity to neutralize a strong acid and it is normally due to the presence of bicarbonate, carbonate and hydroxide compound of calcium, sodium and

potassium. Total alkalinity values for all the investigated samples were found to be greater than the value prescribed by WHO.

Chloride (Cl⁻)

The chloride concentration serves as an indicator of pollution by sewage. People accustomed to higher chloride in water are subjected to laxative effects (6). In the present analysis, chloride concentration was found in the range of 16.9 mg/L to 447.9 mg/L. The values are within the limit except water sample collected from sites S2 and S3. Higher chloride concentration in samples from sites S2 and S3 may be due to big discharge of sewage near the sampling sites.

Total dissolved solids (TDS)

Total dissolved solids indicate the salinity behavior of groundwater. Water containing more than 500 mg/L of TDS is not considered desirable for drinking water supplies, but in unavoidable cases 1500 mg/L is also allowed (7). TDS values varied from 80 mg/L to 1760 mg/L. The sampling points S1, S2 and S3 showed higher TDS values than the prescribed limit given by ISI 10500-91. Phosphate may occur in groundwater as a result of domestic sewage, detergents, agricultural effluents with fertilizers and industrial waste water. The phosphate content in the study area was found in the range of 0.155 mg/L to 0.233 mg/L. Deviations were observed by groundwater samples from municipal water and water quality standards indicating groundwater pollution. Municipal water was found to be fit for drinking purpose than groundwater.

It has been concluded that various pollution parameters of water of the present study with that desirable limit & permissible limit of BIS, Indian standard and maximum allowable limit of WHO reveals that almost all the water sources are below the red line. However all the sources except tube wells and hand pumps are polluted to a little extent.

Regarding fluoride concentration, one well, i.e. WW₂₂ is highly polluted and recorded F⁻ concentration much greater than the maximum allowable limit. The use of its water for drinking purposes should immediately be stopped. WW₁ and WW₁₂ have fluoride

concentration just equal to the maximum allowable limit (1.5 mg/L) and should also be stopped.

1. Several open well have recorded F^- concentration above 1.00 mg/L (i.e. above the desirable limit) and just below the maximum allowable limit. e.g. WW₂, WW₁₀, WW₁₃, WW₁₄, WW₁₅, WW₁₆, WW₁₇, WW₁₈, WW₁₉, WW₂₀, WW₂₂, WW₂₄, and WW₂₅. It shows that the well water of the entire area of Araria District is fluoride polluted. And hence the use of their water for drinking purposes should be avoided. If there is compelling urgency to use their water for drinking purpose, water should be treated before use.

2. The high F^- concentration in drinking water in the entire District is also substantiated by several patients suffering from skeletal deformity.

3. The study revealed that hand pump water and tube well water are least contaminated or not contaminated at all. Hence people of Araria District are advised to use hand pump water or tube well water for drinking purposes.

4. Arsenic concentration in different water resources of the District is well below the desirable limit i.e. 0.05 mg/L in some open well, it is just near to with concentration 0.04mg/L e.g. WW₂ - WW₅, WW₇-WW₁₁, WW₁₃, - WW₂₅. And from this point of view also, open well water should be avoided for drinking purposes.

5. In all the water resources, there is increasing trend of pollution. If this trend continues for next ten year or so, the situation will be alarming in the entire district area. The drinking water will be scarce in the area. So, people of the area are advised to control at least the anthropogenic pollution load in the water resources.

REFERENCES:

1. Raja R E, Lydia Sharmila, J.Princy Merlin, Chritopher G. (2002): *Indian J Environ Prot.*, 22(2), 137.
2. Patil P R, Badgujar S R. and Warke A M. (2001): *Oriental J Chem.*, 17 (2), 283.
3. American Public Health Association (1989): Standard Methods for the examination of water and waste water, 17th Ed., Washington, DC.
4. Trivedy R K and Goel P K. (1986): Chemical and Biological methods for water pollution studies Environmental Publication, Karad.
5. Manivaskam N. (2005): Physicochemical examination of water sewage and industrial effluent, 5th Ed. Pragati Prakashan Meerut.
6. Sudhir Dahiya and Amarjeet Kaur (1999): *J Environ Poll.*, 6 (4), 281.
7. Shrinivasa Rao B and Venkateswaralu P. (2000): *Indian J Environ Prot.*, 20 (3), 161.
8. Adak M D and Purohit K M. (2001): *Poll Res.*, 20(2), 227.